

THE LANGUAGE OF CONFLICT: A TRANSITIVITY-BASED DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF THE ISRAEL-PALESTINE WAR

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Abstract

The conflict has extended beyond the battlefield, the war has manifested in discursive struggles on international platforms, including the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) and the International Court of Justice (ICJ), where competing narratives of legitimacy, victimhood, and statehood are advanced. This paper analyzes the language used by PM Netanyahu and President Abbas at the 79th session of UNGA held in September 2024. The paper draws upon Fairclough's (2013) CDA and Halliday's (2004) Transitivity Analysis, as suggested by Schleppegrell (2013) and O'Grady (n.d), to investigate identity building in the speeches given by the two heads of state by looking at their transitivity system. The findings of the research reveal that on one hand Israel though tries to establish its identity as peace-makers and truth bearers by signaling that whatever atrocities it does are a reaction against the militants of Hamas to maintain the peaceful order of the world; on the other hand, the Palestine equally situates itself as a peace-maker but specifically signals as the victim of Israel and not of any other militant group. It clearly negates initiating any crimes, even in the name of maintaining world order.

INTRODUCTION

The larger Israel-Palestine conflict

For over three-quarters of a century, the Israel-Palestine conflict has been in place, tracing its origins to the mid-20th century, with competing national aspirations and territorial claims ever since the establishment of the State of Israel in 1948 and the displacement of Palestinian Arabs. This marked the beginning of the protracted struggle contested by historical identity conflicts, territorial disputes, and conflicting historical narratives. This conflict is very well-known not only in the Arabian Peninsula but across the world specifically in the Muslim countries particularly for their interest in Bait-ul-Muqaddas, i.e., Jerusalem (a Palestinian city, now a part of the state of Israel), and a mosque in the heart of the city named Masjid-ul-Aqsa, ranked as the third holiest

place for Muslims after Ka'aba, Baitullah, in Mecca, and Masjid Nabvi in Medina. It is not just a mosque but also the qibla-e-awwal, i.e., the first qibla of Islam, to which Muslims first turned to prayer. After delving into the intricate historical landscape and power structures underlying this dispute, researchers contend that the Israel-Palestine conflict remains a profoundly complex and longstanding geopolitical issue, marked by entrenched historical, political, and cultural fault lines (Riman, 2024).

The endurance and complexity of this conflict recently increased about seventeen months ago, on 7th October, 2023, when for the sake of attacking Hamas (an armed political wing functioning in Palestine), Israel attacked and continued to intensify its cataclysmic assault on the occupied Gaza Strip of

Palestine, as per the toll at the time of writing of this paper, killing at least 45,097 Palestinians, injuring at least 107,244, and sieging the territory thereby blocking tons of UN aid (Al Jazeera, 2024) and ever since then Israel has committed the most heinous war crimes (Amnesty International, 2023). On the morning of October 7th, people opened their eyes to a new world where the Israeli settler colonialism, military occupation, and apartheid they had long known promised to escalate to new heights (Isa, 2024). As a matter of fact, over the last sixteen years, the Palestinians of Gaza have paid an insurmountable price for Israeli rage and bloodlust. This is why this paper may refer to the Israel-Palestine conflict as Israel's war on Gaza and/or genocide hereon. This paper, through Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG)'s Transitivity Analysis and Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), uncovers the hidden meanings, power relations, and social identities embedded in the discourse of war. The current study seeks to examine the response of both countries towards this war at the 79th Session of the United Nations General Assembly in New York, during the UNGA debates scheduled 24 - 30 September 2024, almost one year after the war.

This paper explores the intersection of Fairclough's Critical Discourse Analysis (2013) and Halliday's Transitivity System from Systemic Functional Grammar (2004) to explore language choice, power relations, and identities in war zones, thereby building war narratives. To do so, this study investigates the answer to the research question of how does the language used in the speeches of PM Netanyahu and President Abbas contribute to the identity-building of Palestinians and Israelis?

Problem statement

For almost seventy-seven years, the Israel-Palestine conflict has been a crucially grave matter in the geopolitics, history, culture, and geography of the Arabian Peninsula and in the world (Riman, 2024). Though it was always a matter of discussion in academia and scholarship (Jaspal & Coyle, 2014; Abu Khaled, 2020; Rababah & Hamdan, 2019; Cohen, 2015) but its gravity increased after the war broke between the two nations on 7th October 2023 when Israel began its most heinous war crimes on Palestinians and the state of Palestine apparently

against Hamas (Riman, 2024). But as a result, up till now, more than 45,097 Palestinians (Al Jazeera 2024) have been killed, and at least 107,244 have been injured (Al Jazeera 2024). Israel has also sieged the territory, thereby blocking tons of UN aid and humanitarian efforts (Amnesty International, 2023). This has now become a matter of even more significant concern.

Beyond the battlefield, the war has manifested in discursive struggles on international platforms, including the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) and the International Court of Justice, where competing narratives of legitimacy, victimhood, and statehood are advanced (Fareh, 2023; Riman, 2024; Maalej & Zibin, 2024). These discursive battles are not merely rhetorical exercises; they have material consequences, influencing international policies, public opinion, and geopolitical alliances. Political leaders, particularly those representing conflicting parties, use language as a powerful tool to shape identity, construct historical narratives, and justify their actions. Their speeches function as performative acts that seek to legitimize political claims, establish moral authority, and influence diplomatic negotiations.

Given this context, an in-depth analysis of the speeches delivered by Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas and Israeli Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu at the 79th UNGA session (September 2024) offers valuable insights into how linguistic choices contribute to identity-building for Palestinians and Israelis. These speeches are not neutral; they are embedded within larger ideological frameworks that structure how each leader represents their people, frames the conflict, and positions themselves within the global order. Netanyahu's rhetoric has historically employed securitization strategies, drawing on discourses of existential threat, Jewish victimhood, and national resilience, while Abbas has often invoked international law, historical grievances, and human rights discourse to assert Palestinian claims to statehood and self-determination. The way these leaders construct agency, assign blame, and mobilize emotional appeals through their linguistic choices is critical to understanding how discourse functions as a site of power in the conflict.

This paper analyzes the language used by PM Netanyahu and President Abbas at the 79th session of UNGA held in September 2024. This study employs Halliday's (2004) Transitivity Analysis along with Fairclough's (2013) Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), as outlined by Schleppegrell (2013) and O'Grady (n.d.), to examine how the transitivity system in these speeches constructs agency, responsibility, and national identity. By scrutinizing how Netanyahu and Abbas frame their respective positions, this research aims to uncover the discursive strategies that underpin their identity-building efforts and assess their broader implications in shaping global perceptions of the Israel-Palestine conflict.

Research objective

To investigate how the linguistic choices in the speeches of PM Netanyahu and President Mahmoud Abbas at the 79th UNGA session contribute to the discursive construction of Palestinian and Israeli identities, focusing on agency, legitimacy, and victimhood through transitivity analysis and critical discourse strategies.

Research question

How does the language used in the speeches of PM Netanyahu and President Abbas at the 79th UNGA session construct Palestinian and Israeli identities through transitivity choices, agency assignment, and discursive framing of legitimacy and victimhood?

Literature review: Previous discourse studies in the context of the Israel-Palestine war

War narratives are one of the most enduring and complex areas to build in the contemporary world of linguistics. They expand beyond the physical battlefields and territories into the world of words and language. But how do languages form, deform, or reform such narratives like that of war? How do languages construe identities? How is language manipulated to exercise power? All these questions are of immense interest for the researchers around the world who have attempted to explore such discourses. Also, in recent years, scholars have increasingly examined the language, particularly in the context of the Israel-Palestine war.

Al-Addily and Al Shamiri (2024) focus particularly on the discourse produced in the context of the war that broke out on October 7th, 2023, through Van Dijk's comparative critical discourse perspective of SFG's transitivity and role allocation where newspaper articles from Iranian newspapers and American newspapers are taken. The authors found that prejudice tools, defined as the feelings of hostility between groups, were employed in both the newspapers equally, yet there were differences in the way of employment.

On the same lines Assaiqeli (2020), through Wodak and Reisigl's Discourse-Historical Approach of CDA, also examined the non-trivial discourse strategies employed in UN resolutions 242 and 338, along with the lexico-grammatical structures (lexical and syntactic selections) to explore how it influences the Palestinian struggle's realities and the prevailing status quo, despite resolutions aimed at ending the Middle Eastern conflict. Further, it shed light on the role of UN discourse on the right of the Palestinian people to self-determination and the right of return to their homeland. He found that there is a temporization and manipulation in the language used by the UN, even though it's an influential body. Also, since the specifications are not given, the language used is vague, has non-committal statements, contradictions, and creates false commitments, so it does not imply immediate and total withdrawal of Israeli forces.

Further, Malkawi and Fareh (2023) explored the rhetorical and linguistic devices use by Hanan Ashrawi in orations in support of Palestine through the SFL framework, thereby identifying the rhetorical devices used: metaphors, repetition, parallelism, and nominalization to enhance the persuasiveness of advocacy language. They also found that there is a common connection between the thematic patterns identified in the text and the dominant types of processes used.

Apart from the Middle East, the Palestine-Israel conflict has also been a matter of discussion in European scholarship. While Redefining the Genocidal Narrative through a Critical Discourse Analysis of the six 2024 ICJ Speeches in the Genocide Case against Israel, Riman (2024), in Netherlands, through a systematic and an inductive coding using the Corpus Tool #LancsBox v. 4.x.

(2018), found that the South African legal counsels made careful linguistic choices to reflect a strategic effort for persuading the ICJ regarding the genocidal nature of Israel's atrocities, in order to create a broader understanding of the human impact of these actions, and to advocate for the protection and rights of the Palestinian people. Riman (2024) argues that for scholars, researchers and policymakers, such an understanding is pivotal in the examining the role of international legal institutions in conflict and war. Grounded in the definition of genocide, he operationalized the concepts of victimization, individualization, and humanization to highlight the distinct language used that conveys the personal and collective suffering of Palestinians.

Also in England, Jaspal and Coyle (2014) examined the discursive construction, in terms of metaphors and other rhetorical devices, of the Israel-Palestine conflict in speeches by the Prime Minister of Israel and the Palestinian President during the 2011 UN state membership bid.

Likewise, in her research, an Arab researcher Abu Khaled (2020) investigates the manipulation of power and ideology by employing CDA on Netanyahu's speech at the UNGA in 2014 to expose how language is used to justify political actions and ideologies. The research highlights the strategic use of language to frame social actors in particular roles, with Hamas as the active criminal and Israel as the passive victim.

Another Arab scholarship, in a similar context, by Maalej and Zibin (2024) studied the use of animal metaphors in the context of the Israel-Palestine war, with a particular focus on the employment of metaphors that trivialize the Palestinians to justify violence, inhumane discrimination, cruelty and dehumanization. These metaphors serve to portray "Palestinians as less than human, thereby justifying discriminatory treatment and violence against them" (p. 16) thereby making people's perception of them. The research highlights the power of linguistic strategies in constructing social realities and manipulating public opinions regarding the war.

In Jordan, a neighboring country of Palestine Israel, Rababah and Hamdan (2019) analyzed contrastively the speeches of the Israeli PM and Palestinian President, through Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) particularly in the context of the Gaza War of 2014.

They examined how linguistic choices as in terms of transitivity structures not only encode and reflect ideological positions but also construct the in-group and out-group dynamics as victims and peace seekers, and aggressive and destructive, respectively, aligning with Van Dijk's "Ideological Square," where the most central strategies, as they are employed, are the positive self-presentation and negative other-presentation.

Apart from the Middle East, other Arab countries and Europe, the Palestine-Israel conflict has been studied by Israeli scholars too. Cohen (2015), an Israeli researcher within the US scholarship, provides an empirical paradigm for understanding the dehumanization of Palestinians by Israeli ex-soldiers through examining their testimonies by employing psycholinguistic and psychoanalytic tools. He found that the conceptualization of dehumanization occurs as a set of either non-human or sub-human traits and characteristics that are strictly linked with enemy members and so Israeli soldiers view Palestinians as beings that are dangerous and inferior which in turn justifies their violence.

Other than the Palestine-Israel conflict, researchers have also explored identity-building in other areas through CDA. Bayram (2010) elucidates the realization of identity and background in terms of the role of language in political discourse, grounded in Fairclough's CDA, using the World Economic Forum Speech by the Turkish Prime Minister Recep Tayyip Erdogan in Davos. The study, while delving into how linguistic choices vary from speaker to speaker due to identity, mentions that "language has a key role in the exchange of values in social life and transforming power into right and obedience into duty" (p. 27). It also emphasizes the interconnectedness of language and politics.

Similarly, scholars have researched the use of language to achieve other political goals. In this regard, Almahasees and Mahmoud (2022) analyze the persuasive strategies such as intertextuality, creativity, and metaphor employed by King Abdullah II of Jordan in his speeches between 2007 and 2021, to reveal how language is used to achieve a political goal. Thus, the power of language as a tool for reflecting and shaping social realities cannot be denied.

In this study, the terms like war and conflict are used interchangeably. The study, in the context of the war of 7th October 2023 between Israel and Palestine, seeks to critically investigate how through transitivity systems given by Halliday (2004) language is used by PM Netanyahu from Israel and the Palestinian President Mahmoud Abbas build identities in their speeches at the 79th session of United Nations General Assembly in September 2023. This study draws upon the nexus of Fairclough's (2013) CDA and Hallidayan (2004) Systemic Functional Linguistics' transitivity analysis as suggested by Schleppegrell (2013) and O'Grady (n.d).

Theoretical framework: A nexus of CDA and SFG's Transitivity Analysis for identity building and power dynamics

I draw upon Fairclough's CDA (2013) and Hallidayan SFG's Transitivity Analysis (2004), by using the framework provided by O'Grady (n.d), who in his book chapter, illustrates how SFL can be incorporated into a CDA as a framework of analysis since Fairclough's CDA deals with language at three levels and the first one is as a text. He also reviews other works that used the same SFL/SFG as a tool to analyze discourse as text in order to explicate different meanings out of it and explore how language is manipulated in order to form, deform and reform identities, ideologies and power relations. Along with O'Grady I draw upon Schleppegrell (2013) too who explains how 'SFL offers a means of exploring meaning in language and of relating language use to social contexts' (p. 21) in discourse analysis. She argues that Hallidayan SFL recognizes the pivotal role of language in real lives and looks at 'meaning-making as a process through which language shapes, and is shaped by, the contexts in which it is used' (p. 21). SFL facilitates the exploration of meaning in context through a comprehensive text-based grammar. The author suggests that 'SFL has been a popular tool for critical discourse analysis' (p. 28) whether in the fields of politics, mathematics, science, medicine and clinical research on child development and autism. This also adds to the fact by the implication that CDA is trans-disciplinary, like Fairclough argues.

To study the language, in this research, Fairclough's critical discourse analysis (2013), a trans-disciplinary

approach has been employed which is a 'critical social analysis' that focuses on 'relations between discourse and other social elements such as power relations, ideologies, institutions, social identities, etc.' (p.9) in order to understand, evaluate and explain the 'conceptually mediated' (p.9) identities. For such a critical discourse analysis, Halliday and Matthiessen (2004) present Halliday's transitivity analysis from SFL which as a tool of analysis studies how human experiences are construed in language (Haque & Janjua, 2023) and is defined as a grammatical system that construes the world in process types in order to provide its own model or schema. The transitivity system, as Haque and Janjua (2023) state, has six process types given by Halliday. First is the material process, which is the process of physical actions, physical happenings, and physical doings with the performer of the actions as the doer while the object of the action as the goal. The second is the mental process that comprises perception, affection and cognitive abilities sensed by a senser. The senser senses a phenomenon. The third is named as the relational process. Relational process is about having and being. It can either be attributive or identifying. The fourth one is a verbal process and it is about saying a verbiage which is said by a sayer to a receiver. The second last one is a behavioural process, which construes a psychological and physiological behaviour and behavior as its major participant. An existential process, the last of the six processes, depicts the process of existence. The whole transitivity system is accompanied by a circumstances system that is an indispensable part of each process type, comprehended by either prepositional or adverbial phrases, and can be categorized as: the circumstance of extent (level) and location (place, space), of manner (means, quality, comparison), of cause (reason, purpose, behalf), of contingency (condition, concession, default), of accompaniment (comitative, additive), of role (guise, product), and of a matter and angle.

Methodology and data collection: YouTube data, transcription, clausal breakdown and labelling

The videos of both the addresses at the United Nations General Assembly were fetched from the official channel of the United Nations on YouTube. They were transcribed and cross-checked with the

transcript available on timestamps. Then the dataset was broken down in the constituent clauses rigorously and the incomplete or embedded clauses that did not construe any significant meaning were removed. The data was also scrubbed for relatedness and only the clauses that lay in the scope of the study were taken into consideration. These were then labelled for constituents like actors, processes, and circumstances involved.

Analysis and discussion:

The perpetrator or the victim: The representation of Israel at the 79th UNGA

The first part of the data analysis and interpretation section deals with the representation of the state of Israel at the 79th session of the United Nations General Assembly, dated 24 - 30 September 2024. The Israeli Prime Minister, Benjamin Netanyahu, began his speech with the statement that he did not intend to come to UNGA this year because his country is at war. He added that his country is fighting for its life. This implies that it's not a happy, healthy situation around him. Still, then he adds that he was supposed to come because of the "lies and slanders", as he mentioned, that are leveled against his country by the speakers at the podium of the United Nations General Assembly. The addition of these clauses clearly signaled that Netanyahu openly states in a mental process that he did not intend to come but then soon after setting his personal self as I and the sense of the mental process, he brings 'my country' in the role of the active participant i.e. actor of the material process of fight and carrier of the attribute of war that are supported by the circumstance of purpose which is 'for its life'. This shift from 'I' to 'my country' within the first three clauses tends to imply that Netanyahu is actually presenting his country, and whenever he states I, he is actually talking about Israel and whenever he says my country he is implying the same. This claim is based on the fact that that soon after referring to my country Netanyahu goes back to I and in 6 clauses he states I as the actor of the mental process of cognition where he states that I decided which implies that Israel decided and then though some clauses have a phenomena, all of the six clauses using the mental process of cognition are supplied by circumstances of either location or purpose, making

his claims totally valid. This claim is supported by the fact that, shortly after referring to "my country," Netanyahu returns to "I," establishing himself as the actor in six clauses centered on the mental process of cognition. In these clauses, he states, "I decided," implicitly equating his decision with Israel's. While some clauses include a phenomenon, all six cognition-based clauses are accompanied by circumstances of either location or purpose, reinforcing the validity of his claims. By adding circumstances to them, he claims that he decided to come, he decided to set records straight, he decided to speak "for his people", "for his country", "for the truth". All of these imply that Israel does not hold any power as such and is unheard, so a deliberate effort has to be done in order to make it visible to the world. This also indicates that it is not Netanyahu but Israel that was bound to speak for its people, Israel was bound to speak for its country and Israel was bound to speak for the truth. The addition of the clause "[I (Actor) decided (Mental: Cognition) to] speak (phenomenon) for the truth (purpose)" also signals that truth is hidden and what prevails is a lie, so in order to uncover the real truth, a deliberate effort is required.

The following clause, an existential clause, reads as 'Here is the truth'. The use of this existential clause clearly indicates that the unrevealed truth thou not yet uncovered but still is a fact. In a multi-clause sentence with four clauses, Netanyahu states: "Israel seeks peace. Israel yearns for peace. Israel has made peace and will make peace again." Three out of the four clauses are material while one is mental (yearning), showing that Israel is trying every way to make peace in the world. This conflicts with the power dynamics established by Netanyahu in the beginning, where Israel was made to sound helpless, unheard, and invisible with a need to make a deliberate effort. Here Netanyahu makes Israel sound like, using three material clauses, one after the other, the agent of peace that has the power to bring about harmony in the world. To add authenticity, Netanyahu claims that Israel has made peace (in the past) thereby implying that it has already executed the power it holds and has a record.

Further, the speech presents a dichotomy of power dynamics, where "we" (representing Netanyahu and the nation of Israel) and "our enemies" (Palestine,

Hezbollah, and Hamas) are portrayed as opposing forces. The PM emphasizes their side's agency in self-defense and decision-making, framing the "enemies" as aggressors with destructive intent. This strategy is an attempt to mask the destructive events initiated by Israel in Palestine and Lebanon. The power dynamics are contested, with "our enemies" portrayed as wielding aggressive power, while "we" are framed as embodying moral and defensive authority rather than destruction or bloodlust.

Netanyahu further places his group, i.e., Israel ("we") in the position of a righteous defender, acting in response to threats posed by savage and uncivilized enemies (without naming them as Hezbollah or Hamas directly). He also assumes a prophetic or guiding role by invoking historical and religious references, aligning Israel's struggle with timeless and moral narratives from the times prior to the prophet Moses. The word "enemies" here depicts the antithesis of civilization, portrayed as forces of regression and terror that aim to put the followers of Moses into darkness.

In the subsequent two clauses, "We face savage enemies." And "Enemies seek our annihilation." The "enemies" are given active agency as the aggressors by being the doers of the action ("seek our annihilation"). At the same time, "we" are portrayed as targets of this aggression by being the goal/recipient of the action, framing "we," i.e., Israel, as an entity under existential and survival threat. Also, this way, "we" are shown as victims of aggression but implicitly hold moral high ground due to the righteousness of their survival and defense.

Moreover, in the following clause that reads, "We must defend ourselves against these savage murderers," the phrase "must defend" conveys a sense of obligation but helplessness, asserting that power lies with the enemy and Israel is just defending. The term "savage murderers", the source of the crime of murder is a dehumanized one emphasizing the moral justification of self-defense. This clearly establishes "we" as active and resolute defenders of their own existence with limited agency yet righteous and not as perpetrators.

The next set of clauses reads, "Our enemies seek not only to destroy us. They seek to destroy our common civilization...return all of us to a dark age of tyranny and terror." Here, the power dynamic ascribed to the

"enemies" is vast and ominous. Netanyahu frames the adversaries not merely as a threat to "us" but as aggressors targeting a "common civilization" around the world, thus largely implying Palestinians, Hezbollah and Hamas as a threat to the whole humanity and world. This magnifies the scope of their destructive intentions, making them existential foes to shared human values. Netanyahu further implicitly, while emphasizing the stakes of their resistance, elevates the role of "we" as the protectors of this civilization, and thus the protectors of Mother Earth along with all mankind on the surface of this planet. Netanyahu a savior role, positioned to guard universal ideals against tyranny and terror.

Continuing with reflecting on past remarks in "When I spoke here last year...Moses told us that our actions will determine whether we bequeath a blessing or a curse," Netanyahu invokes a figure of immense historical and religious significance. By referencing Moses, the narrative aligns the present struggle with a divine moral tradition. This invocation creates a powerful continuity between the past and present challenges, framing "our actions," i.e., Israel's actions as a moral determinant of future outcomes. In this context, the power dynamic extends to the moral authority that Israel claims to wield, while the position of "we" becomes an embodiment of historical righteousness, charged with shaping a virtuous legacy.

The speaker's narrative then transitions to a pivotal choice: "That is the choice we face today: the curse of Iran's unremitting aggression or the blessing of a historic reconciliation between Arab and Jew." This multi-clause statement introduces agency into the dynamic, shifting from a passive confrontation with aggression to an active decision-making process, bringing Israel to a central position.

The use of the actor "we", due to the power dynamics in play here, not only portrays defenders but also portrays the arbitrators of critical historical points. This choice of linguistic items makes a clear contrast between the destructive and constructive opinions of "curse" and "blessing" (as Moses suggested), thereby situating Netanyahu's group, that is, Israel, as an entity capable of directing the history towards peace instead of conflict (as asked by Moses). Further, in the clause "the blessing I spoke of came into sharper focus", the prime Minister highlights

efforts in achieving the vision of hope and reconciliation as mentioned earlier in another class. The adjective “sharper” in the “circumstance” suggests that there has been a success in achieving this goal of peace despite being in an adverse situation caused by the other group.

Netanyahu uses “we” in the following clause to show that Israel is a forward-moving actor in order to overcome the obstacles put in the way of peace by Palestine. Also, this is where the contrast of the constructive and the destructive vision has clearly been construed. Israel, as Netanyahu signals, is on a constructive path with optimism compared to its enemies.

This dichotomy of power and agency, in terms of peace and otherwise, helps in creating the Identity of peace-lovers for Israel in contrast to Palestine as enemies and hinderers. This also implies that Israel is just shielding against the destructive powers of the enemies and is doing so in order to achieve the goal of historical change in the name of peace as per the commands of Moses.

The perpetrator or the victim: The representation of Palestine at 79th UNGA

The second part of this section deals with the representation of the state of Palestine at the 79th session of the United Nations General Assembly, dated 24 - 30 September 2024. Mahmoud Abbas opened his speech with the clauses that established a defiant tone, with the repeated declaration, “We will not leave.” Here, Abbas positions the Palestinian people as steadfast actors, unwavering in their claim to “Palestine,” described as “our homeland,” “the land of our fathers, our grandfathers,” and something that “will remain ours.” Though it is a promising claim of ownership of the homeland, this opening sounds like a defense as compared to the one made by Benjamin Netanyahu. The relational processes here—“is” and “will remain”—reinforce the identification of Palestine as an inseparable part of Palestinian identity and legacy as projected by Abbas. He then further creates a contrast to assert, “if anyone were to leave, it would be the occupying usurpers,” firmly displacing the legitimacy of the Israeli presence and aligning it with transience and illegitimacy, reddening it as a siege and thus a crime.

The Palestinian Prime Minister transitions to a detailed recounting of actions perpetrated by Israel, identified explicitly as the actor in numerous material processes. The phrase “Israel is perpetrating a crime” establishes the actor’s agency in what is described as “one of the most heinous crimes of our era,” a “full-scale war of genocide.”

This act of clearly naming positions Israel as both the doer of the crime and the moral violator, with the goal or recipient of its actions being the Palestinian people, particularly the “40,000 martyrs” killed, the “100,000 others” injured, and “thousands” buried under rubble. The president specifies that “Israel, the occupying state, is perpetrating a crime” that targets civilians in “Gaza alone,” creating a geographic focus for the violence while underlining its scale.

Abbas mentions that devastation extends to the annihilation of families: “Hundreds of Palestinian families have been annihilated.” The use of a strong material process “annihilated” underscores the absolute nature of the destruction. The specificity of “more than 100 families have been completely wiped out of the civil record” shifts the focus to a strategic erasure, compounding the physical and symbolic dimensions of the loss. This systemic nature is emphasized further with “entire family names have been wiped out,” marking the obliteration of both identity and heritage.

The next clause that reads as “thousands have died because of the spread of disease in epidemics” clearly highlights that the impact of war continues, and so the indirect consequences of violence also increase, thereby shifting the blame on Israel. To supplicate this Abbas adds the clausal circumstance of “shortages in medicine in water”. Here, also the recipient remains the Palestinian people positioned as victims of violence, war, and systematic destruction. Abbas further, in another material clause, adds that “more than 2 million Palestinians in Gaza have left their homes in search of safety”. The use of material processes implies the gravity of the situation. It hints that Israel is not only causing deaths, casualties, injuries, and destruction but also is a culprit behind the displacement (material process) of millions of Palestinians. As Israel is the direct doer of this action and the victim is the Palestinians (direct recipient) of this action, Palestinians are

stripped of agency in this clause, thereby forced to go into a survival mode.

The systematic nature of this war that broke on 7th October 2023 as a planned endeavor of Israel has been reinforced by Mahmoud Abbas in the clause "fleeing the systematic operations that the Israeli occupying army is perpetrating". In this passive clause, the actor is "the Israeli occupying army" while the action of perpetration is supplied by a circumstance of "the systemic operations", thereby signaling clearly about the continued aggression and explicitly naming Israel as a perpetrator of this aggression.

To reiterate his claims, Abbas then says in two relative clauses that "dozens are being killed every day, and double that amount is being injured" to hint at the adversity of the situation as a fact. Mahmoud Abbas, the president of Palestine, also then, while explicitly highlighting the victimization of Palestinians, uses the circumstances of manners as "barefoot people" and location as "in the Gaza strip, the west bank and the Jerusalem."

Furthermore, the speaker rhetorically in a clause adds about "the lies of the Israeli Prime Minister" by saying, "I am not here to respond to the lies". Here, "I" is a pronoun used for both Abbas himself and his nation from the state of Palestine. The speaker signals himself and his Palestinian brothers as the truth bearers seeking credibility against the oppressing army of Israel as liars. The speaker tries to dismantle the assertion of Netanyahu (as truthful) with clauses having rhetorical questions like "who is it then, that killed more than 15000 children and an equal number of women and elderly persons from our people?" Through rhetorical questions the President not only challenges the Israeli Prime Minister but also the audience present at the 79th session of the United Nations General Assembly and the mankind across the globe to differentiate between the truth and lie, between the peace and war, the peace-makers and the perpetrators, between the victims and the violence.

The Palestinian President and the speaker then concluded his speech by uttering the following clauses: "Stop this crime. Stop it now. Stop killing children and women. Stop the genocide." These explicit demands in terms of immediate action by using stop as a material process with immediate goal situate him as an agent of peace calling for

immediate intervention from the global community. This may also imply that humankind across the globe has the power to intervene and stop the war; they may have the power to be enablers of the crime by being silent about the atrocities that happen on a daily basis. He supplies this assumption by saying, as his concluding remark: "The entire world is responsible for what is happening to our people in Gaza and the West Bank". This transfers the blame and agency to the global community, along with Israel, to signal that no one other than Palestinians is adding to peace-making.

Findings and conclusion

The analysis of the data reveals that even though Netanyahu adds the clearest, most vivid details and other elements in its clauses, Israel still does accept bombing Hamas within the vicinity of the state of Palestine in order to control and maintain world order and peace. This may imply killing, injuring, displacing unarmed civilians, and destroying infrastructure and the environment.

On the other hand, Palestine, not even once for the sake of maintaining world order, peace, or the sanctity of religious destinations like the Al-Aqsa Mosque, confesses to doing any heinous crimes. Rather, Mahmoud Abbas of Palestine, through the use of circumstances, relative clauses, and material clauses clearly highlights the victimization of Palestinians at the hands of Israel in Gaza, in the West Bank and in Jerusalem.

Mahmoud Abbas as compared to Netanyahu does sound a little defensive in the beginning as his speech's opening was not as promising as that of the Prime Minister of Israel, but his claim to the Homeland, the motherland and the state of Palestine did indicate Palestinian inherent right to the land and their determination against Israel.

On the other hand, Israel's PM did not mention any claim of owning the land of its country but focused more on the historical and religious background of the state of Israel and commandments of Moses to spread peace and maintain a peaceful world. This implied that Israel has a right and agency to do so, and the rest, in this case, its enemies from Palestine, are trivial and nonexistent in maintaining any peace

The findings of the present study align with the work of Al-Addily and Al Shamiri (2024), who found prejudice and hatred against Palestinians in Israeli discourse, as the findings of the current study reveal, where Netanyahu holds hatred against his enemies, i.e., the Palestinians. Whereas, Assaiqeli (2020) had found that there was a manipulation in the language used by the UN, an influential body, when it came to ceasefire as no specifications were given, the language used was vague, and had non-committal statements, contradictions and false commitments, unlike the findings of the current study where the president Abbas clearly seeks for Ceasefire by saying “Stop it” repeatedly. This repetition is also what was present in Hanan Ashrawi’s orations for Palestinian rights, as found by Malkawi and Fareh (2023).

Maalej and Zibin (2024) believed that Israeli soldiers trivialized Palestinians and the Israeli PM, as this study indicates, does the same by taking up all the agency and stripping them of any position at all in peacemaking. Similarly the findings of this research also align with the findings of Rababah and Hamdan (2019) who after studying the speeches of Israeli PM and Palestinian President in the context of Gaza War of 2014 found that the discourse has contrastive ideological positions as the in-group as victims, and peace seekers and out-group as aggressive and destructive.

In this regard, the present research also highlights the strategic use of language by Netanyahu to frame Palestine in the name of Hamas as an active criminal and perpetuator of violence while Israel as the victim and passive reactor, which aligns with Abu Khaled’s (2020) findings when the speech of Netanyahu at 2014’s UNGA, from a decade ago, was studied. This may imply that the strategic use of language is still the same after 10 years and Netanyahu still uses the same “victim” identity against Hamas.

Since Netanyahu’s rhetorical strategies have remained consistent over a decade, future studies could conduct a longitudinal discourse analysis to track shifts or continuities in Israeli and Palestinian leaders’ rhetoric, particularly in times of conflict and ceasefire negotiations. Since political rhetoric is not limited to spoken or written words, the future research could also explore how visual elements, gestures, and body language in political speeches contribute to meaning-making and ideological

framing. Similar rhetorical strategies might be employed by leaders in other conflict zones. A comparative study could examine whether the victim-perpetrator framing seen in Netanyahu’s speeches appears in the discourse of leaders involved in other geopolitical conflicts.

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